

Influence of increased salinity on yield per plant of rice genotypes. Faisalabad, Pakistan.

Name of mutant or hybrid	Yield (g/plant)			Regression equation	LD ₅₀ (EC associated with 50% reduction over minimum salinity)
	2.4 dS/m	5.0 dS/m	10.0 dS/m		
NIAB-Rice-1	45.5	36.5	22.0	$Y = 52.4515 - 3.0164 X$	9.7
Jhona 349	44.8	30.2	16.5	$Y = 51.3326 - 3.5918 X$	8.1
NIAB-Rice-3 (RST-24)	26.3	23.5	6.0	$Y = 34.7366 - 2.7822 X$	7.7
BSRS-1-85	24.0	20.8	5.3	$Y = 31.4682 - 2.5462 X$	7.7
Basmati 370	23.7	15.7	3.9	$Y = 29.3532 - 2.5724 X$	6.8

dS/m were imposed 1 wk after transplanting, using NaCl in ratio of 4:10:5:1. EC levels were checked daily and maintained at desired levels.

Salt tolerance was estimated as LD₅₀ from the regression equation between salinity level and yield/plant.

NIAB-Rice-1 was the most salt tolerant (see table). □

Integrated germplasm improvement

Rajshree, a new rice variety for rainfed lowlands in Bihar, India

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TCA80-4 (1ET7970) has been released as Rajshree for cultivation in rainfed lowland areas of Bihar. The photoperiod-insensitive mutant from a land race collection from Bhagalpur District will substitute for Mahsuri,

BR8, and other local varieties suitable for up to 25-cm water depth. When transplanted early, Rajshree can tolerate deeper water.

Rajshree yielded higher than checks at Pusa and Patna (Table 1). It has intermediate height (130 cm) and matures in 145 d. It is resistant to bacterial blight, brown spot, sheath rot, false smut, and rice tungro virus (Table 2). It showed relatively better tolerance for drought at vegetative and reproductive stages than Mahsuri in farmers' field trials. With late sowing, it yields better than Mahsuri and has less yield reduction when 60-d-old seedlings

are transplanted.

Grain is medium slender (length 5.8 mm, breadth 2.0 mm, L/B ratio 2.9); 1,000-grain weight is 19 g. Its husk is straw colored and grains are nonchalky. Head rice recovery and cooking and eating quality are better than those of Mahsuri.

In 553 minikit tests in Bihar State 1984-86, average yield was 2.38 t/ha; maximum yield was 4.4 t/ha in Patna District and 5.8 t/ha in a farmer's field in West Champaran District during 1986 wet season. □

Table 1. Yield of Rajshree (TCA80-4) in trials at Pusa and Patna, India.

Variety	Yield (t/ha)										Mean
	1981		1982		1983		1984		1985 ^a		
	Pusa	Patna	Pusa	Patna	Pusa	Patna	Pusa	Patna	Pusa	Patna ^b	
TCA80-4	2.7	2.4	3.1	3.5	3.4	2.4	2.2	1.0	3.0	3.1	2.7
BR8	1.6	2.5	2.9	2.5	2.9	2.9	2.7	1.1	2.7	2.6	2.4
Mahsuri	na	2.3	2.8	3.2	3.8	2.3	2.2	0.4	2.4	2.8	2.5
LSD 0.05	0.7	0.9	1.5	0.6	0.7	0.3	0.7	0.1	0.2	0.2	
CV (%)	22.9	19.8	27.2	15.0	12.0	6.9	17.2	44.9	4.0	8.4	

^aWater depth was 80 cm in Pusa, and 50 cm in Patna. ^bBelkunda Chaur. ^cMikki Chaur.

Table 2. Reaction of Rajshree (TCA80-4) to rice diseases.

Variety	SES ^a score (0-9 scale)				
	Tungro ^b	Brown spot	Bacterial blight	Sheath rot	False smut
TCA80-4	3	3	3	3	3
BR8	7	5	7	3	5
Mahsuri	9	5	7	5	7

^aStandard evaluation system for rice. ^bBased on natural incidence in 1980 wet season at Pusa.

Evaluation of upland rice lines at Morogoro, Tanzania

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We evaluated 12 upland rice lines from various research centers. Each line was direct sown at 20- × 20-cm spacing in the field under rainfed conditions during the 1987 cropping season, in a randomized complete block design with three replications.

Soil was sandy, with pH 6.4, 2.6% organic matter, and 0.16% total N. Particle size distribution was 90% sand, 8% silt, and 2% clay. Fertilizer was 60-60 PK/ha at planting and 100 kg N/ha, half at tillering and half at panicle initiation.

Overall, yields were poor, from 1.8 t/ha for IRAT104 to 0.3 t/ha for OS6 (Table 1). IRAT104 and IRAT161 significantly outyielded local check

Table 1. Means for the variables studied and total rainfall for each rice line during the 1987 cropping season at Morogoro, Tanzania.^a

Cultivar	Total rainfall (mm)	Duration (d)	Yield (t/ha)	Plant height (cm)	Mean panicle length (cm)	Tillers/plant (no.)	Harvest index (%)	Filled grains/panicle (%)	Drought effect score (0-7)
Farox 229	297.4	140.0 abc	0.9 bc	73.0 cd	15.1 d	5.0 b	26.0 ab	44.0 b	1.8 b
IRAT104	297.1	135.0 d	1.8 a	78.3 bc	17.8 ab	6.0 ab	46.0 a	65.0 ab	1.7 b
IRAT156	297.4	139.3 bc	0.8 bc	76.0 bcd	18.4 ab	6.0 ab	48.0 a	89.0 a	1.7 b
IRAT161	297.1	129.3 e	1.3 b	78.3 bc	16.8 bcd	8.0 a	31.0 ab	63.0 ab	2.0 b
IRAT170	293.8	126.7 f	0.4 cd	66.3 de	15.7 cd	7.0 ab	31.0 ab	50.0 ab	2.7 a
ISA6	297.4	138.7 c	0.9 bc	70.0 cd	19.3 a	6.7 ab	31.0 ab	60.0 ab	2.0 b
ITA128	297.1	135.0 d	0.8 bc	68.0 cde	17.2 bc	7.3 ab	26.0 ab	51.0 ab	2.2 ab
ITA235	293.8	124.0 f	0.7 bc	76.0 bcd	18.6 ab	8.0 a	28.0 ab	56.0 ab	1.8 b
ITA305	298.3	125.3 f	0.8 bc	58.0 e	15.5 cd	6.7 ab	43.0 ab	53.0 ab	2.2 ab
ITA315	293.8	122.3 g	0.4 cd	68.3 cde	16.9 bcd	8.3 a	17.0 b	51.0 ab	1.8 b
OS6	297.1	138.0 c	0.3 d	84.7 ab	16.7 bcd	5.3 b	26.0 ab	46.0 ab	2.4 ab
Supa	297.8	146.7 a	0.4 cd	93.3 a	18.6 ab	7.0 ab	19.0 b	41.0 b	2.7 a
\bar{X}		133.4	0.80	74.2	17.2	6.8	31.0	56.0	2.1
SX		0.7	0.18	3.4	0.6	0.7	8.0	7.3	0.2
CV (%)		0.9	38.5	7.7	6.1	17.9	17.7	23.2	16.8

^aIn a column, mean values followed by the same letter do not differ significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) by DMRT.

Table 2. Simple correlation coefficients between the variables studied in the upland rice lines at Morogoto, Tanzania, 1987 season.^a

Variable	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
1. Drought effect	-											
2. Days to maturity	-0.127	-										
3. Plant height	0.176	0.612*	-									
4. Panicle length	-0.169	0.514	0.451	-								
5. Tillers/plant	0.067	0.444	-0.169	0.253	-							
6. Panicle weight	-0.570*	-0.029	0.039	0.261	0.095	-						
7. Filled grains/panicle (%)	-0.637	-0.024	-0.152	0.407	0.123	0.872**	-					
8. Harvest index	-0.406	0.015	-0.274	0.036	-0.352	0.669*	0.745**	-				
9. Panicles/m ²	0.238	-0.498	-0.273	0.235	0.629*	-0.111	0.036	-0.277	-			
10. 1000-grain weight	0.243	-0.192	-0.173	-0.703*	-0.371	-0.274	-0.359	-0.075	-0.198	-		
11. Plants/m ²	0.228	-0.280	-0.373	0.301	0.604*	0.088	0.233	0.004	0.722**	-0.139	-	
12. Grain yield	-0.608*	0.099	-0.029	-0.125	0.097	0.808**	0.672*	0.599*	-0.163	0.126	0.131	-
Significance of regression on yield ^b	(-ve)*					(+ve)*		(+ve)*				

^a*, ** denote significance at $P < 0.05$ and 0.01 , respectively. ^bMultiple regression when all the variables were included in the equation.

Supa. The low yields were attributed to drought, particularly during the reproductive stage, between booting and grain filling. After two rainless weeks

then, we provided two supplemental furrow irrigations a week.

Panicle weight and harvest index had positive effects on seed yield (Table 2).

Panicle weight, filled grains/panicle, harvest index, and yield were positively associated. □

Yield potential of IR7167-33-2-3 and Tainan V at Ndop Plain, Northwest Cameroon

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Rice, a relatively new crop in Cameroon, is grown on about 20,000 ha

of irrigated lands. Ndop Plain at an altitude of 1,200 m above sea level in the Northwest Province is one of the three major rice production areas. The primary constraints to increased productivity are low temperature and associated severity of sheath rot (ShR) and grain discoloration (GID).

Tainan V, a popular traditional variety, has bold, short, chalky grains and poor keeping quality. IR7167-33-2-3 was released for general cultivation in

1987. It has medium-long, less chalky grains, and fair keeping quality. It yields higher than Tainan V, is low temperature tolerant, and resistant to ShR and GID. It is also 8 d shorter in duration.

We examined the yield potential of the two varieties over several seasons from on-station and farmers' field trials. The on-station yield trials used early transplanting at 25- × 20-cm spacing, 2-3 seedlings/hill, and 60-40-40 kg